

WAYS OF DEVELOPING THE GREEN ECONOMY FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Currently, the idea of transition to a "green" economy is being discussed not only in our country, but all over the world. The transition to a "green" economy will help to solve environmental problems such as unwise use of water resources, air pollution, deforestation, land degradation and climate change.

The instability of the current development trends in the world, the turmoil of the world economy, and the growing imbalance of economic, social and environmental trends make it necessary to form new economic models. Such formation should be carried out within the framework of the paradigm of sustainable development, which has taken a central place for humanity in the 21st century.

The need to form a new economy is clearly necessary to think about the response to the growing environmental problems that threaten human civilization. That was the essence of this thinking. The report of the International Commission on Environment and Development, Our Common Future (1987), was well expressed, and in fact became the basis for international and national conceptual documents in the field of sustainable development: "The economy is not limited to the creation of wealth, but ecology does not refer only to nature conservation; both concepts are equally aimed at improving human well-being."

According to foreign experts, in order to transition to a "green" economy, 10 environmental skills that are common in various fields of production, namely: design, leadership qualities, management skills, energy, urban planning, landscape design, communication travel, waste management, purchasing and financial skills are in high demand.

A green economy is an economy that aims to reduce environmental risks and ecological scarcity and achieve sustainable development without destroying the environment. It is closely related to ecological economics, but has a more politically applied orientation.[1] The Green Economy report states that "to be green, an economy must be not only efficient, but also fair. Fairness involves recognizing global and country-level dimensions of equity, particularly ensuring a just transition to a low-carbon, resource-efficient and socially inclusive economy.

A green economy is defined as low carbon, resource efficient and socially inclusive. Attract public and private investment in economic activities, infrastructure and assets that enable employment and income growth in a green economy, reduce carbon emissions and pollution, improve energy and resource efficiency, and prevent the loss of biodiversity and ecosystem services is done through.

These green investments should be activated and supported through targeted public spending, policy reforms, and changes in taxation and regulation. The United Nations promotes a development path that understands the environment, natural capital as an important economic asset and source of social benefits, especially for poor people whose livelihoods depend on natural resources. The concept of a green economy is not a substitute for sustainable development, but creates a new focus on the economy, investment, capital and infrastructure, employment and skills, and positive social and environmental outcomes throughout Asia and the Pacific.

In the period of modernization of the world economy, transition to many updated innovative technologies, the driving force of development is considered to be a factor of economic efficiency. However, it should be noted that it is important to prevent their negative impact on the quality of life and living environment of the population. Due to this, the "green" strategies implemented by the countries are being supported.

There is no "one-size-fits-all" recipe for implementing green growth strategies. An economy's path to greening growth depends on policy and institutional conditions, the level of development, resource availability, and specific environmental pressure points. Developed

and developing countries face different opportunities and challenges, as do countries with different economic and political conditions.

On the other hand, there are general points to consider in all directions. Above all, good economic policy lies at the heart of any green growth strategy. In a flexible, dynamic economy, enabling growth to be the best factor - green growth. Development of greening requires more, efficient use of resources is necessary to minimize ecological pressure. At present, efficient use of resources and its management is the main goal. Economic policy and many fiscal and regulatory interventions not normally associated with the "green" agenda are involved. And in any case, policy action requires not only consideration of a very broad range of policies, but also a broad emphasis on traditional "green" politics.

The Green Growth Strategy focuses on mutually reinforcing aspects of economic and environmental policies. It takes into account the full value of natural capital as a factor of production and its role in growth. It focuses on cost-effective ways to reduce environmental pressures to influence the transition to new forms of growth.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the experiences of many foreign countries regarding the "green economy" have been studied, and the implementation of many measures in the field of "Greening" is one of the most important programmatic issues in the framework of ecopolitics. In particular, the basin of the main rivers in our region and the reduction of biological diversity are causing serious concern. Evaporative gases and large-scale air pollution are exacerbating the problem

In conclusion, the international aspect is very important in the transition to sustainable development. On the one hand, many environmental problems are universal and common to most countries. On the other hand, their solution often depends on the joint, coordinated actions of the world community.

Until recently, economic science did not pay enough attention to the transition to sustainable development and environmental problems. This was one of the reasons for the formation of man-made type of economic development. This type can be characterized as a

nature-intensive (nature-destroying) type of development, which means that it is based on the use of artificial means of production created without taking into account environmental constraints. The characteristics of the man-made type of characteristic development are as follows: rapid and complete use of non-renewable types of natural resources (primarily minerals); excessive use of renewable resources (soil, forests, etc.) at a higher rate than the possibilities of their reproduction and restoration; volumes of pollution and emissions that exceed the assimilation capacity of the environment.

Therefore, we must first of all meet the needs of the population and increase the creation of material benefits in order to increase their well-being, standard of living and quality without harming ecology and environment. Secondly, energy resources are needed for production and economic development, and I believe that it is necessary to increase them at the expense of renewable energy sources, replace public transport with electric ones, and build energy-saving buildings.